

Notes Toward a Semiotic Description of Economic Value

Gianni Cresci

Preface

This text is presented as a faithful—though not strictly literal—revision of a piece written in 1994, circulated at the time only in typed form, intended for a few close readers and later made available online many years afterward. It derives from *Gli argomenti del valore. Appunti per una semiotica del marketing*, whose structure and the near-totality of whose original formulations are retained here. Although the English title no longer reproduces the original one, this edition maintains conceptual continuity with the 1994 manuscript, whose core intuition—an attempt to address the problem of economic value from a semiotic perspective—was already, even then, independent of the operational framework of marketing.

Thirty years later, I considered it worthwhile to revisit that text, freeing it from the terminological and pragmatic framework within which I had initially situated it and returning it to the theoretical terrain that already constituted its implicit horizon: the economic process of value-exchange, in its cognitive, interpretive, and argumentative articulations, as well as in the preliminary moments of ideation, design, and production of the object. In this new version, marketing appears only as one among the applied knowledges that have engaged with this process, while the center of gravity of the inquiry shifts deliberately toward more general questions.

In most cases I have preserved the 1994 formulation in its entirety. This edition is the result of a process of subtraction rather than rewriting: I removed the terminological apparatus tied to marketing and replaced certain operational expressions, allowing the original theoretical core to emerge. I have not altered the argumentative structure, nor have I introduced clarifications or developments from later years: the present edition does not incorporate theoretical retrofitting, nor does it attempt to reinterpret the text retroactively in light of subsequent literature. The bibliography therefore remains essentially the same as in 1994, suitably purged of references that were exclusively instrumental to the marketing industry.

In the 1990s I proposed a distinction between “marketing theory” and “the marketing-object,” drawing—albeit in a deliberately adapted form—on the traditional differentiation between object-semiotics and metalanguages. By “marketing-object” I did not mean the discipline, but the ensemble of economic practices: design, production, distribution, promotion, interpretation, and consumption. In other words, the process through which an object is valorized and exchanged.

In the present edition I have chosen to preserve this conceptual insight without retaining its terminology. The reference to the “marketing-object” is therefore replaced by the broader and more theoretically neutral expression “economic practices of valorization and exchange,” which more precisely captures what that term was intended to designate at the time: not a discipline, but a process.

What interests me is not updating the essay according to the current state of the art, but making newly legible the theoretical core it already contained, and which remains, in my view, a useful standpoint from which to address several problems still open today—particularly the possibility of a semiotic description of the processes that precede, structure, and render economic exchange possible.

This new edition does not aim to conclude a trajectory, but to reactivate it, bringing back into view a theoretical core that, then as now, still seems to me worthy of discussion. In a subsequent work, I hope to confront more explicitly the hypotheses advanced in 1994 with certain more recent developments in semiotics and in economic thought, in the conviction that a theory of value understood *sub specie semiotica* may offer a non-marginal contribution to contemporary debates.

For the moment, I limit myself to returning this text in its most essential form, faithful to the original premise that neither objective nor subjective theories of value—taken in isolation—are able to account for the complexity of the processes that structure value-attribution; and that understanding such a process requires a careful return to the object, to its determinations, and to the regimes of pertinence that guide its evaluative investment.

All translations from Italian are the author's.

Gianni Cresci
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1. The process of exchange

The analysis of the economic practices that articulate processes of valorization and exchange commits semiotics to engaging with a set of heterogeneous forms of knowledge—often not fully systematized—that in recent years have sought, at times as autonomous disciplines (as in the case of marketing), to define their own object of study. Although these bodies of knowledge sometimes highlight the absence of a general theory and of an adequate descriptive language, they have nonetheless equipped themselves with procedures of discovery and generalization. The inductive method, followed by the identification of constants and hypotheses of regularity, has made it

possible to postulate individual laws that have not, however, provided an answer to the demand for simplicity and generality.

By contrast, a deductive procedure has mainly come to characterize the semiotic approach to the description of the economic process of valorization and exchange: proceeding from general properties of processes of signification, semiotics seeks to deduce specific features of the economic phenomena associated with exchange.

The deductive procedure finds its justification not so much in the reduced or indeterminate dimensions of the object, but in the fortunate circumstance that semiotic theory possesses a descriptive language formally adequate—at least in an initial phase of definition—to the economic practices of valorization and exchange. Exchange, in particular, presents itself as a process in which values are invested in goods and which presupposes a logically prior interpretive and evaluative act.

The object that economic analysis is called upon to describe is therefore a semiotic process: there is no exchange without someone deciding to interpret the good as a sign of something. That is, there is no exchange without semiosis. However, for exchange to take place a merely cognitive act of interpretation is not sufficient: the virtualization of values, apprehended as pure difference, must be followed by an act of value attribution.

What is at stake, then, is not the semiotic character of the process of exchange, but the criteria of value judgment—that is, the modes by which value investment occurs. And it is on this very issue that the different currents of economic thought have long confronted one another. Not even the opposition between the subjective theories of the neo-classicals and the objective theories of the neo-Ricardians— to cite a relatively recent manifestation of the controversy—has in fact found a solution: the theory of value remains an open question. Yet while economic theory appears capable of elaborating an autonomous theory of prices, the analysis of exchange practices cannot, by contrast, dispense with a defined theory of value.

On the other hand, neither the theories of absolute value—in their various formulations—nor the theories that appeal to utility functions or to mathematical orderings of rational preference decisions account for the complexity of the process that precedes exchange. We believe that precisely the need for a new vantage point—one capable of placing labor-value theses, utility-value theses, and those that also take into account other parameters such as the scarcity of goods within a single coherent theoretical framework—calls semiotics into play.

For the moment, many authors seem instead to linger over pseudo-materialist premises that detect everywhere vague “dematerializations” and “evaporations” of the object’s truths: its functionality, its straightforward “use-value,” its physicality—reduced to “pure exchange-value” by an uncontainable “symbolic.” The implicit proposal to homogenize oppositions such as “materiality” / “immateriality,” “use-value” / “exchange-value,” “functionality” / “symbolicity,” is the sign of a confusion that is not merely terminological. And while referential fallacies and theories of needs reappear, increasingly insistent reference is made to post-industrial culture as the cause of the

“transformation of the commodity into a sign,” as if an object and its “use-value,” understood here as the set of its virtual functions of use, were not already correlated by a sign-function, and as if the exchange of goods did not, in any case, have to involve a process of symbolization. (cf. Eco 1975: 40)

2. Pertinences

If exchange presupposes an act of value-attribution, the latter necessarily implies an act of cognitive interpretation. Even before it arises in terms of evaluation, the question of value is in fact posed in terms of pertinence.

Among the various bodies of knowledge which, in the economic and managerial domain, have addressed the phenomena of exchange, marketing thought—in its operative applications—has always felt the practical need to keep the two issues distinct: that of the interpretation and positioning of a good, and that of its value. The task of a more general economic theory of value is, however, today that of accounting for the ways in which descriptive values, purely positional values, or even values already “endowed with a thymic connotation” (Greimas 1983: 97) and thus axiologized, are modalized by value-judgments. In other words, the task is to investigate the relation of reciprocal influence that links the attribution of value and the traits made pertinent through interpretation.

3. Value

Value-investment is theoretically independent of both the virtualization and the very axiologization of a semic entity. The modal structure of the subject of state recategorizes the value-systems it takes in charge, modalizing axiological values into desirable or non-desirable ones (Greimas 1983: 97–98). Yet the value-judgment operates upon a semantic space already made pertinent by the cognitive act. The very hypothetical and interpretive nature of knowledge entails the actualization of certain content-traits—entails, that is, a choice of pertinence that functions as the regulative criterion of the evaluative trajectory. The practice on which pertinence depends is, in the case of the interpretation of a good, strongly oriented by projectual considerations. Characterized by an asymmetrical regime of information, the market of consumer goods nonetheless constrains the evaluating subject (the consumer, in a broad sense) to issue value-judgments: the interpretation of a good may thus present itself as a “collection” of traits in view of an evaluation. And this search for indexes is characterized by inferential procedures that involve abductive efforts of various levels. The fact that some inferences, owing to their apparent immediacy, appear to us as virtually “automatic” should not make us forget that within the very “tension of recognition there is already semiosis” (Eco 1990: 14), and that “the issue in the everyday practice of semiosis is to recognize a signifier as a signifier. And to do that one needs a certain interpretive effort” (*ibid.*: 12).

Granted, then, that a certain specificity of the “post-industrial object” may be admitted, we hold that such specificity cannot lie—as some authors would have it—in the idea that the object “becomes a sign,” for it already functions as one, but rather in the increasing complexity of the interpretive procedures the subject must mobilize in order to judge it. The coexistence—within the same culture—of different value-habits prompts the consumer to wager, each time and depending on contexts and circumstances, on the very adequacy of the criteria of judgment. This is why we maintain that the scarcity of a good, the labor required to produce it, or the ensemble of its functions of use should not be considered “value-bearing substances,” but semantic properties of the object, actualized by value-habits imposed by the subject.

The evaluative process is therefore complex not only because of the inferential procedures that characterize it, but also because the very adoption of the value-habit that conditions those procedures is itself the result of a hypothesis and— as we shall argue later—an object of intimate deliberation: that is, the outcome of an argumentative process.

While, in order to extract indices concerning the rarity of a good or the amount of labor required to produce it, the evaluating subject must set a conjectural mechanism into motion—one that enables, for example, the inference of information about the production process through the interpretation of certain physical traits—the price presents itself already as a proposed axiological contract that concerns the value of the good. Yet the axiological contract is a fiduciary contract, and between price and value there is no relation of identity but rather one of semiotic referral. Price can be used to lie, and “whenever the possibility of lying arises, we are in the presence of a sign-function” (Eco 1975: 89). We know that price is often interpreted as an index of a good’s value, and it is by now well known that one can inventory the circumstances and contexts that determine its appropriateness for the evaluating subject. Analyses of the same kind could likewise be conducted with respect to other prevailing value-habits and to the interpretation—under determinate circumstances—of other properties as indicators of quality.

We believe that semiotics can provide adequate tools for this purpose. For it should be clear that when we speak of “indicators of quality” we are referring to pertinences through which a good has been known and evaluated: any semantic property of the object—its availability, its virtual functions of use, the labor required to produce it, or any other description—may be actualized. In other words, something functions as an indicator of quality when someone decides to interpret it as such.

4. Individual Subject and Social Subject

The adoption of a value-habit entails the acceptance of a series of presumptions that may display varying degrees of generality. To decide to orient one’s value-judgment on the basis, for example, of the degree of availability of a good means having accepted the presumption that the value of a commodity depends on its rarity. In this case, the presumption exhibits a certain degree of generality.

But the evaluating subject is necessarily brought to confront the individual practices that guide pertinent selection and value attribution with the pertinences and evaluative perspectives it takes to be shared by the social subject. This confrontation, which takes an argumentative form, may be marked by significant conflict. We know well that disagreement between the individual subject and the social subject concerning values is far from infrequent: one need only consider how the collective subject may sanction the passions that derive from faulty evaluations of objects. And in any case, value is by definition the “manifestation of a polarity”: indeed, “every value judgment, while consisting in a gesture of attribution, also entails a polemical aspect—that is, the rejection or the respect of competing and allied attributions” (Calabrese 1987: 17).

We hold that, rather than maintaining a contraposition between objective and subjective criteria of value—whose outcome, as the history of economic thought has taught us, is decidedly uncertain—it is preferable to replace that opposition with an analysis of the relations between the values shared by the social subject and those upheld by the individual subject.

5. Judgment as Deliberation

As we have seen, the question of value arises not only in terms of a greater or lesser interpretive tension, but above all in the coexistence, within the same culture, of different value-habits. The subject constructs hypotheses and must decide, each time, the parameter through which a good is to be known and evaluated. Characterized by a regime of hypotheses and dialectical tests, the cognitive process leading to judgment has an argumentative nature; and evaluative doing has little to do with evidence or necessity: we are, in fact, in the domain of the plausible and the probable.

An adequate semantics should allow the analysis of processes of exchange — as well as applications of marketing and, in a broader sense, reflections on an economic theory of value — to identify the selections operated by arguments upon the sememe that has found manifestation in that specific product.

We consider Stefano Traini’s (1994) proposal for the description and construction of marketing strategies to be among the most convincing for the perspectives we have adopted. The encyclopedic-format model should indeed allow the description of a semantic space susceptible to argumentative reorganizations. Traini’s model is articulated within the interpretive-semiotic framework developed by Umberto Eco, from which it draws both its encyclopedic conception of semantic space and its emphasis on inferential operations.

Yet it seems to us that the very effectiveness of that proposal depends on its ability to account for the syntactic form of objects of value (cf. Greimas 1991). It is therefore not, in our view, crucial to identify the properties governing “the syntagmatic relations with other consumer objects” (Traini

1994: 75), as also suggested by the so-called syntagmatic approach to commodities (Kehret-Ward 1987).

Rather, we believe that the true objective should be to analyze how the syntactic properties of the object represent a network of constraints for the subject's evaluative trajectory (cf. Greimas 1991).

6. The Economic Process

The arguments we have discussed are also shaped by the type of audience to which they are addressed: in the case of intimate deliberation, the audience is “the subject himself, when he deliberates or sets out for himself the reasons for his acts” (Perelman 1958: 33). But along the path that leads from design and production to commercialization, the product may become the object of different valorizations. We must indeed reasonably assume that the angles of pertinence through which a retailer and a potential consumer view the object of exchange may differ considerably. The same difference may arise, for the very same object, between the retailer and the producer.

Moreover, it is also likely that the same actor may assume different value-habits and adopt different arguments depending on the interlocutor: consider how the same product is presented by the same company to the consumer and to the trade. And if we imagine situations typical of longer distribution processes, we see other actors emerging — such as the sales agent or the dealer — for whom the argumentative process may take the form of a dialogue with a single interlocutor (*ibid.*).

The multiplicity of audience types, arguments, and value-habits that punctuate the economic process should not discourage analysis, but rather stimulate the search for common traits and for the formulation of a metalinguistic framework adequate to the various phases of the process.

In order for a semiotics of economic practices to be constituted, it seems to us that one must proceed precisely from questions that pertain to general semiotics, understood as a “reflection on the conditions of possibility of specific semiotics” (Eco 1985: 331). The first and most ambitious objective that semiotics can set for itself with respect to economic processes is the same that general semiotics once assigned to itself, namely that “phenomena that are superficially different may be spoken of in a unified manner” (*ibid.*).

For this reason, we insist so strongly on the hypothesis that the phases of the economic process — although in many respects so different from one another — may nonetheless be characterized by a common inferential and argumentative procedure, regardless of the subjects of communication and representation involved.

Even the analysis of advertising discourse, according to the perspective we propose, should account primarily for the pertinences established by the argumentative process — pertinences that remain, so to speak, available for possible value-investments. Since “from a semiotic point of view a product is an object constructed by a mixture of properties that includes every kind of information about it”

(Proni 1994: 227), the question that the analysis of the advertising text should answer is precisely the one Proni poses for himself in the case of automobile advertising: “If a car is also composed of descriptions, and since advertising is a description of the product, in what way does advertising determine the set of semantic properties that constitute the automobile?” (*ibid.*: 278).

7. Toward an Eccentric Approach to the Object and to the Economic Theory of Value

The debates that have sought to draw a sharp distinction between pragmatically oriented disciplines and scientifically oriented ones do not seem to us particularly fruitful—especially when they are mobilized to problematize the encounter between semiotics and those bodies of knowledge that intervene in processes of valuation and exchange. In reality, a scientific practice is not defined by its distance from its own applicative domains, but by its capacity to articulate—on the basis of a knowledge of its object—programs for the possible modification of that very object.

A scientific practice should, in fact, also be able to “permit, once its object has been known, programs for the modification of that very object” (Eco 1985: 328). Yet it is clear that, before verifying the possibility of intervening in order to modify or enhance its object, theory must first describe it.

Among the disciplines concerned with analyzing processes of valuation and exchange, some are particularly invested in programs for the modification of their own object. This is the case, for example, of marketing theories. But it is clear that, before verifying the possibility of intervening in order to modify or to favour its object, the theory must first describe it. The definition of the process of valuation and exchange proposed in the first chapter—necessarily incomplete—appeared to us adequate for an initial description.

Let us now attempt to draw certain consequences from the hypotheses we have posited and discussed, in light of the perspective adopted on the process of valuation and exchange. Two ideas have implicitly guided our discussion. The first derives from the hypothesis that the cognitive and evaluative procedures that logically precede the act of exchange can be described within a broad framework that takes “the decisions and actions of human beings as the outcomes of inferential processes” (Bonfantini 1982: 113). This theoretical premise has allowed us to hypothesize the analysis of the various moments of production and commercialization according to a common and verifiable perspective.

The second hypothesis is that sememes are *meaning effect* independent of the semiosis that manifests them (Marsciani–Zinna 1991: 33). This means “that the course of sense traced by the sememe may find its contextual manifestation as much in a lexical item of a natural language as in a drawing” (*ibid.*). Like the lexeme, the exchangeable good may be considered a complex configuration of virtual sememic potentialities, actualized from time to time through interpretation. Sememes themselves cannot be regarded “as a collection of semes, the products of a purely

combinatory operation,” since they often connect — “implicitly,” as Greimas and Courtés note — “actantial structures” and “thematic configurations” (Greimas–Courtés 1979: 309).

This is why we hold that the analysis of processes of valuation and exchange requires a suitable semantics capable of accounting for the reorganizations of semantic space produced by interpretive and argumentative practices.

In light of what we have argued so far, we maintain that an encounter with semiotics should induce applied knowledges—including marketing theory—and, on the theoretical side, the various economic theories of value, to pursue a renewed orientation toward the product: a *return to the object* and to its determinations. This would amount to translating strategic activity itself into the systematic and preliminary investigation of the possible pertinences of the object. In other words: we hypothesize and hope that one may begin from the syntactic organization of the object and formulate hypotheses concerning the practices that will guide its interpretation and valorization in the subsequent phases.

Yet we imagine this sort of *return to the object* as effective only if situated within a theoretical framework in which the process of valorization and exchange is apprehended in its complexity and eccentricity. And with the awareness that, in the first place, economic value theory—as well as, in a more limited sense, traditional marketing strategy—must itself become eccentric.

Every description, every argumentation, and every judgment of value that characterizes any of the phases of ideation, production, and commercialization contributes to the very definition of the object of exchange. The solid hierarchical ordering of the phases of the economic process thus dissolves into a set of decentralized decision-making areas.

It is precisely the recognition of the eccentricity of the entire system that may enable economic value theory, marketing theory, and a semiotics of marketing—still in the process of being defined—to focus attention on the crucial moments in which value is determined. A value that does not present itself to the subject as an evidence, but as the convincing and provisional resolution of an argumentative process.

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